

Synthesis of Some 6-Substituted Pyrimidines*

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As shown by Roy *et al.*¹, some 2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-(substituted amino) pyrimidines exert interesting inhibitory effect on a number of micro-organisms. It was therefore considered to be of interest to study the effect on the inhibitory activity of small changes in the nature of the substituents in the 2- and 4-positions of the pyrimidine ring. For this purpose, several 2,4-dihydroxy-6-(substituted amino) pyrimidine derivatives were previously synthesised². We have now synthesised some 2-hydroxy-4-amino (compounds I-V) and some 2,4-diamino-pyrimidines (compounds VI-VIII) having similar substituents in 6-position. A new 2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-substituted pyrimidine (compound IX) has also been synthesised. 5-Nitroso derivatives (compounds X-XV) of some of the above compounds have also been prepared.

I.	R=OH ;	R ₁ =NH ₂ ;	R ₂ = <i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ NH-
II.	R= „ ;	R ₁ = „ ;	R ₂ = <i>p</i> -IC ₆ H ₄ NH-
III.	R= „ ;	R ₁ = „ ;	R ₂ =C ₄ H ₈ NO-, H ₂ O.
IV.	R= „ ;	R ₁ = „ ;	R ₂ =C ₃ H ₁₀ N-
V.	R= „ ;	R ₁ = „ ;	R ₂ =-NH-
VI.	R=NH ₂ ;	R ₁ = „ ;	R ₂ = <i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ NH-
VII.	R= „ ;	R ₁ = „ ;	R ₂ = <i>p</i> -IC ₆ H ₄ NH-
VIII.	R= „ ;	R ₁ = „ ;	R ₂ =-NH-, HCl.
IX.	R= „ ;	R ₁ =OH ;	R ₂ =C ₃ H ₁₀ N-

X.	R=OH ;	R ₁ =NH ₂ ;	R ₂ = <i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ NH-
XI.	R= „ ;	R ₁ = „ ;	R ₂ = <i>p</i> -IC ₆ H ₄ NH-
XII.	R= „ ;	R ₁ = „ ;	R ₂ =C ₄ H ₈ NO-, H ₂ O.
XIII.	R= „ ;	R ₁ = „ ;	R ₂ =C ₃ H ₁₀ N-
XIV.	R= „ ;	R ₁ = „ ;	R ₂ =-NH-
XV.	R=NH ₂ ;	R ₁ = „ ;	R ₂ = „

*To be treated as "Pyrimidines. Part VII".

1. Arch. Biochem. Biophys., 1961, 92, 366.
2. Paul and Sen, Indian J. Chem., 1964, 2, 212.

Compounds (I-III) were prepared by refluxing 2-hydroxy-4-amino-6-chloropyrimidine³ with a slight excess of the corresponding amine in water-ethanol (2:1) mixture in presence of a few drops of HCl according to the method of Banks⁴. Compounds (VI-VII) were prepared in a similar way by reacting the corresponding amines with 2,4-diamino-6-chloropyrimidine⁵⁻⁶. The reaction of 2-hydroxy-4-amino-6-chloropyrimidine with cyclohexylamine in aqueous ethanolic medium in presence of HCl was, however, slow and the yield of the product (V) was very low. Compound (V) (and also IV) was therefore prepared by heating the chloropyrimidine under reflux with excess of the corresponding anhydrous amines. Compound (III) could also be prepared by this method in slightly higher yield. Compound (VIII) was prepared in a similar manner from 2,4-diamino-6-chloropyrimidine and anhydrous cyclohexylamine and compound (IX) from 2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-chloropyrimidine⁷ and anhydrous piperidine. The compound (VIII) was obtained not as the free base but in the form of hydrochloride. Its 5-nitroso derivative was, however, obtained in the form of free base.

TABLE I
Properties and analytical data of the pyrimidines (I-IX).

Compound No.	Pyrimidines,	M.P.*	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
I	2-Hydroxy-4-amino-6- <i>p</i> -bromoanilino-	350°	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₄ Br	C : 42.50% H : 2.90 N : 20.30	42.70% 3.20 19.92
II	2-Hydroxy-4-amino-6- <i>p</i> -iodoanilino-	340°(d)	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₄ I	C : 36.15 H : 2.31 N : 17.45	36.56 2.74 17.07
III	2-Hydroxy-4-amino-6-morpholino-	334°(d)	C ₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ ·H ₂ O	C : 44.95 H : 6.59 N : 25.95	44.85 6.54 26.10
IV	2-Hydroxy-4-amino-6-piperidino-	**	C ₉ H ₁₄ ON ₄	O : 55.67 H : 7.43 N : 29.19	55.67 7.21 28.86
V	2-Hydroxy-4-amino-6-cyclohexylamino-	328-29°(d)	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ ON ₄	C : 57.84 H : 7.96 N : 26.50	57.69 7.69 26.92
VI	2,4-Diamino-6- <i>p</i> -anisidino-	194°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ON ₅	C : 57.39 H : 6.80 N : 29.92	57.14 6.62 30.30
VII	2,4-Diamino-6- <i>p</i> -iodoanilino-	206-207°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₅ I	C : 36.93 H : 3.40 N : 21.16	36.69 3.05 21.40
VIII	2,4-Diamino-6-cyclohexylamino- (hydrochloride)	221-22°	C ₁₀ H ₁₇ N ₅ ·HCl	C : 49.25 H : 7.57 N : 28.40	49.28 7.39 28.74
IX	2-Amino-4-hydroxy-6-piperidino-	334-35°(d)	C ₉ H ₁₄ ON ₄	C : 55.57 H : 7.20 N : 28.86	55.67 7.21 28.86

*Melting points were determined in capillary tubes on a copper block, Melting points of compounds that melted with decomposition were determined by introducing the compound in the block at a temp. 10° below its m.p. and by heating the block further at the rate of 4°/min.

d denotes decomposition.

**Gradually decomposes above 330°.

3. Wheeler and Jamieson, *Amer Chem. J.*, 1904 **32**, 342.

4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1127.

5. Roth *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1950, **72**, 1915.

6. Pfeider and Lehrmann, *Chem. Ber.*, 1961, **94**, 12.

7. Forrest *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3.

For purification, compounds (I, II, IV, V, and IX) were crystallised from ethanol, compounds (III, VI and VII) from water, and compound (VIII) from a mixture of benzene and ethanol (10:1).

Compounds (I-V and IX) are insoluble in common organic solvents and water. Compounds (VI-VIII) are soluble in ethanol, methanol, acetone, ethyl acetate, and dioxane but insoluble in benzene. Compounds (III-VII and IX) are soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid but the hydrochloride derivative (VIII) is soluble in water.

Under similar experimental conditions, 2-hydroxy-4-amino-6-chloropyrimidine was found to react much more rapidly with the amines than 2,4-diamino-6-chloropyrimidine.

The 5-nitroso derivatives of compounds (I-V and VIII) were prepared by adding a solution of equimolar amount of sodium nitrite in water to the solution of the corresponding pyrimidines in water or glacial acetic acid containing traces of water below 10°.

Of these, compounds (X-XIII) were crystallised from ethanol and compounds (XIV and XV) from water. All of these possess characteristic colour. Compounds (X-XIV) are insoluble in common organic solvents and water, but compound (XV) is soluble in ethanol. All of these, however, are soluble in dilute HCl.

The melting points and other data of compounds (I-IX) are recorded in Table I and those of the 5-nitroso derivatives in Table II.

TABLE II

Properties and analytical data of the 5-nitroso derivatives (X-XV)

Compound No.	Pyrimidines,	*M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
X	2-Hydroxy-4-amino-5-nitroso-6- <i>p</i> -bromoanilino-	292°(d)	Reddish brown	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ N ₃ Br	22.95	22.58
XI	2-Hydroxy-4-amino-5-nitroso-6- <i>p</i> -iodoanilino-	300-301° (d)	Deep orange	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ N ₃ I	19.23	19.60
XII	2-Hydroxy-4-amino-5-nitroso-6-morpholino-	**	Violet	C ₈ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ ,H ₂ O	29.19	28.80
XIII	2-Hydroxy-4-amino-5-nitroso-6-piperidino-	***	Blue	C ₉ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃	30.99	31.39
XIV	2-Hydroxy-4-amino-5-nitroso-6-cyclohexylamino-	290-91°(d)	Pink	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	29.13	29.53
XV	2,4-Diamino-5-nitroso-6-cyclohexylamino-	225-26°	Red	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ ON ₆	35.92	35.60

*d same as in Table I.

**Gradually decomposes from 240°

***Gradually decomposes from 270°.

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